

Effective Use of Content as a Feature in IMDB Dataset Analysis

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Abstract

This study explores the effectiveness of machine learning techniques for movie rating prediction and genre validation, utilizing comprehensive datasets from IMDb and TMDB. Gradient Boosting algorithms and Decision Trees are employed for rating prediction, emphasizing the balance between accuracy and computational efficiency. The Sentence Transformer embeddings combined with a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model are leveraged for genre validation, transforming textual movie overviews into vectorized formats to identify genres with high accuracy. Results indicate that the Gradient Boosting Regressor yields superior performance for rating prediction, achieving an optimal balance between precision and computational speed. Additionally, the CNN model demonstrates substantial success in genre validation tasks, reflecting its capability to process complex textual data and identify associated genres effectively. The findings underscore the importance of integrating content-based features in enhancing predictive accuracy for movie analytics.

Keywords:

Movie rating prediction, Genre validation, Machine learning, Sentence Transformers, CNN

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1911, Ricciotto Canudo, an art critic, introduced the term "seventh art" to describe cinema in his Manifesto of the Seven Arts (Welsh, 1975). Canudo believed that film combined several different artistic forms into something entirely new. With the inclusion of sound and colour, combined with widescreen formats, cinema started extending its cultural influence globally. Nowadays, movie ratings and genre selection can offer insights into various areas, including psychological interpretations (Puhazhli and Francis, 2023).

Studies based on IMDb data leverage various machine learning models and historical data for the purpose of

accurately predicting movie ratings. In one prediction of movie ratings using historical data such as actors, directors, genres, content ratings, and production companies reported that a 1D CNN model achieved optimal performance with an MSE of 1.20 and an MAE of 0.83 (Abarja & Wibowo, 2020). Another investigation demonstrated the effectiveness of the XGBoost algorithm, which attained an MAE of 0.656 for movies rated between 1.0 and 10.0 (Zabaleta de Larrañaga, 2021). A study introduced a hybrid recommendation engine that combined collaborative filtering with machine learning techniques, achieving an RMSE between 0.8959 and 0.97613 via an Alternating Least Squares (ALS) model (Awan et al., 2021). Content-based filtering is a system that

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recommends items with similar characteristics based on users' past preferences or interactions. It is commonly employed as an initial filtering method in movie recommendation systems (Musa & Zhihong, 2020; Sanwal & Çalıřkan, 2021; Nair & Preethi, 2022).

The movie genre validation task can be conducted through research studies that examine data extracted from full plots. Short summary/ overview plot—this, gives a general view of the movie's core story, summarizing the main theme and events into a few sentences, usually without giving a bigger perspective. A detailed summary/full plot provides information about the structure of the narrative, the relationships among characters, and other aspects of its development.

Too Many Cooks 1931- Overview Plot: A young couple, soon to wed, begin building their dreamhouse, but their interfering relatives cause no end of trouble.

Too Many Cooks 1931- Full Plot: Al Bennett and Alice Cook are blissfully happy and are building their house in an isolated area, using Al's savings of \$7,000. Troubles begin when Al's uncle and boss, Uncle George, unaware of Al's engagement, inspects the house and announces he will live with him. Furthermore, he wants Al to marry Minnie Spring, a wonderful girl George just met, so the three of them can live happily ever after. Troubles mount when Alice's parents come to see the partially built house. They bring with them eleven other family members, some of whom expect to live with the couple when they marry. Badgered on all sides, Al finally yells "There's too many Cooks." Alice breaks their engagement, and George fires him. As if these problems weren't enough, the Carpenter's Union calls a strike, but a determined Al decides to finish the house himself. Months later, lonely and depressed, Al puts his finished house up for sale, but things are looking up for Al.

In studies utilizing plots, the F-score of 56% was achieved using the Gated Recurrent Units (GRU) model (Hoang, 2018). In another study, applying Topological Data Analysis (TDA) methods led to a significant 15% improvement in the F-score, achieving 71.88% (Doshi and Zadrozny, 2018). An F-score of 67.68% was obtained in genre prediction from film summaries using Bidirectional LSTM (Bi-LSTM) (Ertugrul and Karagöz, 2018). In a study utilizing AI-generated movie titles and plots from 10 different genres, the data was vectorized and used to train a sequential neural network model. The model achieved approximately 80% accuracy in predicting movie genres (Tanvir et al., 2023).

In this study, the performance of machine learning models is evaluated using TMDb and IMDb data for rating prediction and genre validation tasks. Gradient Boosting algorithms are applied as the primary method for rating predictions, providing accurate and efficient outcomes. For genre validation, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model is employed. Plot overviews are transformed into vector representations using Sentence Transformer embeddings, enabling CNN to identify patterns and validate genres based on the provided plot data.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Rating Prediction Regression

Comprehensive data from IMDb is gathered to predict movie ratings. The IMDb datasets include basics.tsv, ratings.tsv, and title.principals.tsv, which are merged using the unique identifier tconst. From the IMDb datasets, the file basics.tsv is used to extract entries where the title type is "movie," retaining the columns tconst, primaryTitle, startYear, and runtimeMinutes. The file ratings.tsv provides the columns tconst, averageRating, and numVotes, while the file title.principals.tsv contributes the columns tconst, nconst, and category.

These datasets are merged based on tconst values, filtering records where numVotes exceed 999. Furthermore, categories such as "actor," "actress," "producer," "writer," "editor," "composer," "director," and "cinematographer," which appear more frequently than the total number of movies, are selected from the category field in title.principals.tsv. These categories are then formatted as lists in the corresponding fields within the dataset and converted into a structured format. A pivot transformation restructures the categorical data, organizing it into distinct feature groups. The transformed features integrate with the original data frame for further analysis.

A systematic approach is required to handle data in machine learning, particularly with large datasets like IMDb. Reading methods that can handle various formats and compressions are essential for loading large-scale external datasets. Multiple datasets are combined into a single dataset for use in machine learning models, with relevant entries filtered and essential columns retained to ensure that only useful information contributes to model training.

Data processing involves several strategies. The strategy focused on processing Nconst values consists of cleaning the data by removing leading characters (nm), converting valid entries into numeric form, and padding them with zeros to a specified length to ensure uniform vector lengths. Another approach encodes genre lists as unique bases- 24 numbers for efficient storage and retrieval during subsequent analyses involving genre-based groupings or comparisons. Each genre is assigned a unique code, enabling the creation of an encoded number representing multiple genres within a single entry. Additionally, a quantile-based binning and normalization strategy is applied to vote count distributions, ensuring an even spread across predefined bins and normalizing counts to a range between 0 and 9.99.

Feature preparation for movie rating prediction involves encoding categorical variables. Actors and actresses are assigned up to 10 attributes, while directors, writers, producers, editors, composers, and cinematographers are limited to 4 attributes each. Missing values in all categories

are padded with "0" to ensure uniformity. Numerical attributes include release year, runtime, and the number of votes, which are normalized. Genres are encoded as unique identifiers to enable efficient processing in regression and classification models. This process generates a 48-dimensional feature vector for each movie, which is used for rating prediction through regression analysis.

To prepare the data for machine learning, target variables are binned, scaling is applied, and the dataset is partitioned into training and testing subsets with stratification to

ensure balanced distribution across bins. Once training is completed, predictions are made on new data to assess the model's ability to generalize to unseen examples. The model's performance is evaluated using metrics such as Mean Squared Error, which emphasizes larger prediction errors, and Mean Absolute Error, which quantifies average prediction errors. Root Mean Squared Error reflects errors in the same units as the original data, while R-squared measures the proportion of variance explained by the model.

Figure 1. Handling IMDb data

Figure 2. Preprocessing IMDb data

Decision trees are a type of predictive model that tests conditions in the data, where each branch represents a condition, and each leaf node corresponds to an outcome (Rudin et al., 2022). Gradient Boosting Machine is a function estimation method that uses numerical optimization in function space (Friedman, 2001).

Unlike traditional parameter estimation methods, the issue of function approximation is treated in a more general gradient descent boosting paradigm. In Gradient Boosting Decision Trees, decision trees are built sequentially, and the model for each tree is created by fitting the negative gradient.

Boosting models create a predictive model by combining many weak classifiers, each of which builds on the

performance of the previous tree. GBDT encompasses various methods, including XGBoost and CatBoost. XGBoost and CatBoost. XGBoost is a gradient boosting approach that combines decision trees with regularization to enhance predictions to help prevent overfitting (Szczepanek, 2022).

CatBoost handles categorical data, featuring techniques such as ordered boosting, which assists in minimizing overfitting, making it efficient for large datasets. However, it is sensitive to hyper-parameter tuning compared to other GBDT algorithms, and its performance heavily depends on this tuning (Hancock & Khoshgoftaar, 2020).

Figure 1 demonstrates the handling of IMDb data, focusing on data extraction and integration. Figure 2 highlights

preprocessing techniques, including feature transformations and scaling, to prepare the data for

modeling. Figure 3 visualizes the distribution of average ratings.

Figure 3. Distribution of Average Rating

2.2. Genre Validation

Genre validation utilizes short movie plots from TMDB and genre definitions sourced from IMDb's help page. The genres assigned to each movie come from IMDb, with each film including at least one and at most three genres. For movies with multiple genres, each genre functions as a distinct input. Rare genres, representing

less than 0.1% of the dataset, and movies without TMDB synopses are excluded. Films with multiple genres appear as distinct entries, expanding the dataset size from 40,376 to 94,347 samples. Negative examples emerge through random assignment of unrelated genres within the dataset, matching the number of positive samples to create a balanced dataset with 94,347 additional negative examples.

Figure 4. Merging text data

For movie genre prediction, film overviews and genre definitions are transformed into numerical representations that capture semantic meanings using sentence embeddings. Text vectors are obtained through the “paraphrase-MiniLM-L6-v2” model (Reimers, 2019),

which is trained with a bi-encoder neural network based on the BERT model (Reimers & Gurevych, 2020). These vectors have 384 dimensions, as the bi-encoder reduces the standard 768-dimensional BERT vectors by half. Inputs containing multiple sentences, such as some film

overviews, are also processed as single inputs and converted into 384-dimensional vectors.

The model utilizes the embeddings of the movie overview and the genre definition to determine whether the genre is associated with the movie. These embeddings are processed through a convolutional neural network (CNN) model designed for movie genre validation. Contrastive learning is applied to positive and negative examples.

Data augmentation involved splitting entries with multiple genres into separate records for each positive genre and generating an equal number of negative examples for non-associated genres. Negative examples result from pairing movie plots with unrelated genres, ensuring equal representation that enhances the model's generalization. This approach addresses the imbalance in the distribution of positive associated genres by creating an equal distribution of non-associated negative genres. The validation model trains on the augmented dataset to predict associated and non-associated genres based on the provided definitions. The dataset is divided into training, validation, and testing subsets through stratified sampling, ensuring balanced distributions across all sets.

Genre verification employs two-dimensional Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and a text matching approach to classify genres as associated or unrelated to movies. The CNN is trained on pairs of overview and genre embeddings, and its performance is evaluated.

The Neocognitron model, featuring a multilayered hierarchical structure with self-organization capabilities and enabling object recognition from different perspectives, was inspired by biological visual systems (Fukushima, 1980). This model is one of the first artificial neural networks with a "deep" structure, introducing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and implementing neurophysiological insights (Schmidhuber, 2015). In 1989, LeCun and colleagues applied the backpropagation algorithm to convolutional neural networks with weight-sharing mechanisms, similar to the Neocognitron (LeCun et al., 1989). Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are feedforward neural networks designed to automatically extract features from data through convolution operations (Li et al., 2021). 1-dimensional convolution filters are typically used for text classification in CNNs (Jacovi et al., 2018).

Figure 5: Distribution of Genres

In this study, genres are processed as text using genre definitions, and the task is approached as a relationship between two texts, employing a 2-dimensional CNN. Text matching and contrastive learning methods function as key strategies in training the 2D-CNN model. These methods enhance the model's ability to differentiate between genres associated with a movie and unrelated ones, contributing to improved genre validation performance.

In the proposed model, the input layer has an input shape of (2, 384, 1), allowing it to take a pair of overview and genre embedding. This architecture includes three 2D convolutional layers with 32, 64, and 128 filters, each using a (1, 2) kernel. ReLU activation is applied to each convolutional layer, followed by batch normalization. Max Pooling layers with a pool size of (1, 2) reduce dimensionality while preserving important features. Dropout layers with a rate of 0.5 mitigated overfitting.

4. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This study underscores the effectiveness of machine learning techniques in analyzing and predicting movie ratings and validating genres using IMDb data. Attributes such as release year, runtime, category, director, and cast are found to play a significant role in determining film ratings. The Gradient Boosting algorithm demonstrated strong performance in regression tasks, achieving low error rates, with an MSE of 0.711 and an MAE of 0.607, showcasing its ability to effectively integrate categorical and numerical data into predictive models.

For genre validation, a two-dimensional CNN model utilizing text embeddings was developed. The model successfully identified patterns by representing movie plot summaries and genre definitions as numerical embeddings. The application of contrastive learning to distinguish between associated and non-associated genres resulted in an accuracy of 84.45%. This approach highlights the importance of optimizing input representations to improve learning outcomes in limited data scenarios.

The findings illustrate a robust framework for predictive modeling and genre classification in the entertainment industry. By combining advanced machine learning models with strategic data preparation and representation techniques, the study provides valuable insights into content-based analysis for movie analytics. Future studies can build upon these results by exploring alternative neural architectures and additional features to further enhance predictive accuracy and classification performance.

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